

Digital media and digital divides: an exploration of primary school-age children's use of and access to digital media

Katrin Potzel (orcid.org/0000-0002-5317-6945)

Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nuremberg, Germany

Abstract

The article presents an in-depth analysis of the digital divide regarding children in middle childhood and its implications for educational institutions. It focuses on how children's access to digital media, their media usage, and related skills vary significantly, influenced by socio-economic backgrounds and family environments as well as peer contexts. As basic framework, the article highlights three levels of the digital divide: access to digital media devices and infrastructure, differences in media usage and media-related skills, and the impact of these disparities on formal education. With empirical data from the longitudinal qualitative study *ConnectedKids – Socialisation in a Changing Media Environment* (ConKids), the article illustrates how the digital divide manifests in the age of primary school. It shows that children's media repertoires and competencies are diverse and influenced by their family environment, leading to varying levels of media literacy and therefore possible influences in educational outcomes. The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted these disparities, as distance schooling requirements exposed the gap between children's media usage at home and school. The article concludes with challenges for educational institutions deriving from these empirical insights, emphasising the need to consider children's varied media backgrounds and competencies in curriculum development and teaching practices. It suggests that addressing these disparities early in education is crucial for promoting inclusive media literacy and ensuring equal opportunities for digital participation.

Keywords: media socialisation, digital divide, primary school, qualitative longitudinal study.

Introduction

Digital media are a self-evident part of our current society: Smartphones, tablets and the Internet can be found in almost every household. In 2023, 91% of individuals aged above ten years in Europe owned an own smartphone and 93% of Europe's whole population used the Internet (International Telecommunication Union (ITU), 2023). This omnipresence of digital media devices and applications as well as an increasing connectivity, differentiation, speed of innovation and datafication is summarised under the term of *deep mediatisation* (Hepp, 2019). The societal meta process of deep mediatisation can therefore describe the changing media environment as well as associated transformations of social interaction and communication. Consequently, media practices in the private sphere are a natural part of growing up, individual development and socialisation (Kapella et al., 2022; Livingstone & Lunt, 2014; Smahel et al., 2020). Nevertheless, children's individual media habits differ greatly, whether because of their own preferences and interests or because of social influences such as media experiences in families and peer groups (Paus-Hasebrink et al., 2019). The fact that social diversity can explain these differences is widely discussed under the heading of "digital divide" (Hargittai & Hsieh, 2013; van Dijk, 2020). Deep mediatisation (Hepp, 2019) further reinforces the trend towards a digital divide, revealing an increasing diversity in children's *media repertoires*. The term media repertoire refers to the entirety of all different media that a person regularly uses in combination with the according media practices (Hasebrink & Popp, 2006) and in ways that not only differ within an age group, but also in relation to dynamic changes in media devices, applications and topics children grow up with.

At the latest in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, media use is becoming increasingly important in the school context (Vuorikari et al., 2020). Due to the different media experiences and prerequisites of children from the private context, however, it seems to be easier for some of them to adapt to the schools' *media ensemble* – which consists of all media of a social domain and their spatial arrangement (Hasebrink & Hölig, 2017) – and to meet the academic media literacy¹ requirements as for others. However, these prerequisites have hardly been taken into account, e.g., in the current digital education action plan by the European Union (European Commission, 2020). On the contrary, the focus is mainly on normative categories and objectives, as well as technical competencies, while children's individual media repertoires and experiences are hardly considered. Nonetheless, according to the European Commission, the promotion of digital skills and competencies for children should start at the primary school level to support them in their later educational and career paths and enable them to participate digitally in the society.

Against this background, this article addresses the following questions: In which ways do children's individual media repertoires and competencies differ throughout the period of

¹ Media literacy in this article is defined as the ability to use digital technologies to access, analyse, evaluate and communicate information in a variety of digital platforms (Buckingham, 2007).

their primary school attendance as their first formal educational environment? What patterns are emerging with regard to informal and formal educational media usage? And which conclusions can be drawn for the context of formal education? The article highlights these topics on the basis of empirical longitudinal data from the *ConnectedKids – Socialisation in a Changing Media Environment* (ConKids) project². The panel study examines the socialisation process of children and adolescents, with the focus in this article on middle childhood (age from six to ten years) and data collected from 15 families in Germany between 2018 to 2022.

Digital Divide in middle childhood

To explain differences in children's access to digital media devices, software and data infrastructure, various terms and approaches have been used in educational and media research such as "digital divide", "digital exclusion" or "digital inequality" (Sanders, 2020). The overview in this article refers mainly to the concept of digital divide as used by van Dijk (2020). So, on a first level, the chapter addresses the *differences regarding digital access of children* and how this access is socially entangled. On the second level, it highlights *differences in media usage and media-related skills and competencies* also in dependency of social influences. On a third level, the question of how these differences in digital access, media usage and skills can have *outcomes for formal learning in educational institutions* will be addressed.

Differences in children's digital access

Following the argument of van Dijk (2020), who uses a four-layered framework to distinguish between four kinds of access to digital media infrastructure, the "first level digital divide" today extends well beyond mere access to digital media devices (1 – physical access). It encompasses all differences in usability for their intended purposes such as the device type or Internet speed (2 – material access), whether there is sole access to the respective devices or if they need to be shared (3 – conditional access), as well as one's own attitude towards the specific applications (4 – motivational access).

As mentioned before, the majority of children aged above ten years in Europe possesses their own smartphone (93% in 2023), around 81% of European households had a computer at home in 2023 (ITU, 2023; statista, 2024). The purely quantitative figures suggest that households are well equipped with digital devices, but it is also clear that a small proportion of the population does not have access to digital media at home – for example in the UK this fact is discussed under the heading of data poverty if citizens do not have sufficient financial means to afford access to digital infrastructure. These differences must be taken into account as inequalities in physical equipment. Furthermore,

² The research project *Socialization in a changing media environment* is led by Rudolf Kammerl (Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nuremberg) and Claudia Lampert (Leibniz Institute for Media Research, Hans-Bredow-Institut) and funded by the DFG (KA 1611/7-1 and LA 2728/1-1).

such figures do not provide any information on the extent to which the hardware is state-of-the-art.

The situation is similar regarding Internet usage: In 2023, two in three people globally used the internet (ITU & UNESCO, 2024, p. 3). In Europe, the number is even higher, including 91% of individuals using the Internet in 2023 (ITU). Despite the widespread use, differences can also be identified here e.g., regarding the access to a fast internet connection. In rural regions of Europe in particular, there are still major deficits regarding access to the Internet (ITU, 2023).

In terms of physical access, families can be said to be very well equipped, too. Though, (younger) children often don't have their own devices, they frequently share devices with siblings or parents. The proportion of children having their own devices is increasing over time and as they grow older. The smartphone appears to be the most important device for children starting at an age of nine, whereas desktop computers and notebooks continually play a minor role (Smahel et al., 2020). Current figures from Germany show that by 2023, 36% of children between the ages of three and thirteen have their own smartphone (compared to 4% fewer in 2019) (Guth, 2023). The percentage of children with their own devices rises dramatically with increasing age: while the proportion of children between the ages of three and five is only three percent, the first jump is up to 30 percent between the age of eight and nine, 73 percent between ten and eleven and 93 percent between 12 and 13 (ibid.). In contrast to the growing number of children having their own devices, parents are restricting children's media usage as part of their parental mediation – so children do not always have access to the devices themselves or individual applications (Livingstone & Blum-Ross, 2020; Smahel et al., 2020). Especially with younger children, parents often intervene through setting time or content-related rules, use access blocks or apps to check or limit certain devices as well as applications (Livingstone & Blum-Ross, 2020; Livingstone & Sefton-Green, 2020; Wahyuningrum et al., 2020). Furthermore, children have different interests when it comes to using (digital) media, which is why they access different types of devices and applications. Whether, for example, media that are important in school or later professional context are also used by children in their free time therefore depends heavily on their own motivation (e.g., mpfs, 2022; Ofcom, 2024).

Differences in children's media usage and media-related skills

In recent years, researchers have recognised a 'second-level digital divide' which concerns not only types of usage of digital media but also digital skills (van Dijk, 2020). Whether children search for entertainment, communication or information in a digital environment, is very individual and is becoming increasingly differentiated (Ofcom, 2024; Smahel et al., 2020). These usage behaviours are also mediated by social domains, e.g., regarding socio-economic background, their media practices or concepts. Thus, the family as the first socialisation instance plays a decisive role in the different types of usage and therefore the media repertoire of children (Di Pietro et al., 2020; Paus-

Hasebrink et al., 2019). Due to the family-specific media ensemble, children initially have a specific selection of certain media practices exemplified to them by their parents and siblings. Parents are not only deciding on access to specific devices, but also on the applications used (Livingstone & Blum-Ross, 2020; Mascheroni et al., 2018). The norms and values of parents around gender and by gender stereotypes can, too, influence decisions about which media (content) is offered, encouraged or prohibited to children (Lünenborg & Maier, 2013). With increasing age, other social domains beyond the family become more important for access to certain media practices, e.g., school or peers (Di Pietro et al., 2020; Paus-Hasebrink et al., 2019).

Building on the individual disparities in access to media offerings, there are differences in children's media-related skills and abilities. Although children and young people are often assumed to have the necessary digital skills simply because they have grown up in a deep mediatised society, current empirical findings show that they often overestimate themselves and do not make optimal use of digital media's potentials (ECDL, 2018). Furthermore, cross-national comparative studies such as PISA or the ICILS point out differences in children's media-related skills due to social or socio-economic disparities (Di Pietro et al., 2020; Fraillon et al., 2019). Because it becomes evident that parents are the main contact person for their children regarding media topics or emerging media-related challenges (Smahel et al., 2020), their attitudes towards certain media practices or contents (Vittrup et al., 2014) as well as their media-related skills also play a decisive role. Depending on how capable they are in assisting their children in acquiring such competencies, the existing gap can be further widened and can even lead to digital exclusion (Coleman, 2021).

Differences in outcomes for formal education

In recent years, the outcomes of these first two stages of the digital divide have been discussed under the term third-level digital divide (van Dijk, 2020). This third-level aims at understanding the impact of the digital divide's first two stages on offline inequalities. It relates to "gaps in individuals' capacity to translate their internet access and use into favourable offline outcomes" (van Deursen & Helsper, 2015, p. 30). In the context of formal education, for example, one can understand this divide as the effects of technology access, use and skills on educational performance (van de Werfhorst et al., 2022). Especially, since digital media are becoming increasingly important in school contexts (UNESCO, 2022; Vuorikari et al., 2020), the different media practices and competencies have to be taken into account in educational institutions. However, in international educational research, there are very few empirical results regarding this matter. This changed abruptly due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which brought about distance schooling and a significant increase in media usage in educational institutions.

A recent study by Müller and Goldenberg (2020) in the UK highlighted that, according to 88 percent of teachers asked, some of their students had no access to the internet or devices needed to enable distance schooling. Furthermore, they reported that only 44%

of their students had learned how to use the new technologies required for remote learning. A difference between the perceptions and relevance of teachers and children regarding media literacies has already been identified by Burn et al. (2010). Parkin and colleagues (2020) illustrate this gap from the perspective of parents of primary school pupils: here, 64% of parents stated they were confident that their children had all the necessary skills for distance schooling. In contrast, 16% reported difficulties their children faced during this time. This implies that children with fewer digital skills likely encountered issues participating in remote learning, thus limiting their formal educational opportunities. Especially when children lack appropriate digital skills or any form of access to digital media, parental involvement is crucial in assisting them overcoming these challenges of the digital divide (Julius & Sims, 2020; Lucas et al., 2020; Montacute & Cullinane, 2021). This illustrates that parental support plays an important role in this matter or as Coleman puts it: "Children whose parents do not have the digital skills and time to support them in digital distance learning are more likely to be digitally excluded" (Coleman, 2021, p. 10).

Methodology and Methods

This article wants to trace these different levels of the digital divide using empirical data from the *ConnectedKids – Socialisation in a Changing Media Environment* (ConKids) longitudinal study. In the context of researching media socialisation, the individual media repertoires and skills of children can be analysed, entangled with the conditions in the social domains in which they are integrated (in the study's context: family, peers and school).

In the course of the study qualitative interviews in 32 families in North and South Germany were conducted, each with one child and one parent. The longitudinal data collection took place in 2018 (t1), 2019 (t2) and 2022 (t3)³. The sample is divided into two cohorts: the younger children were all ten years old in the survey 2022 and the older ones between 14 and 15 years. The parents were asked to send in photographs of the media their child used before getting interviewed. These were used to create a media-actor relationship together with the children and as a conversational stimulus for guided interviews with the children and one parent each. In the third wave, the children also filled in media diaries. These diaries provide information about the role of different media in everyday life and were likewise used primarily as a stimulus to identify media repertoires and to reflect on the children's media practices in the qualitative interviews with both themselves and their parents. The interviews also covered the media literacy perceptions of parents and children as well as media-related learning processes in informal and formal contexts. As the survey took place before and after the COVID-19 pandemic and therefore the last interviews after the distance schooling during the pandemic, it was possible to ask about changes during and after this exceptional situation for families and educational institutions. The study received approval from the Ethics Committee of the

³ A further round of interviews took place in the first half of 2023. However, this data is not included in the analysis here.

German Educational Research Association (04/2017/GERA). Prior to participating in the study, all participants provided their informed consent for inclusion. All collected data were transcribed and evaluated using qualitative content analysis (Kuckartz & Rädiker, 2023).

To explain differences at the end of primary school in the individual media repertoires we focus on cases of the younger cohort ($N=15$). The longitudinal data from three surveys, beginning shortly after the children started school (age of six to seven), allows us to look not only at a single moment, but at the individual developments until the end of primary school (age of ten). Keeping all cases of the younger cohort in mind, the results will be illustrated by four selected cases to highlight where deep mediatisation emerges as a driver for the different levels of the digital divide and how these diversities influence formal learning with digital media in educational institutions. Table 1 shows an overview of all cases, the four cases selected are highlighted and were pseudonymised with the names Emil, Felix, Frieda and Isabell. The cases were selected on the basis of different socio-economic and family circumstances as well as differences in media repertoire, media-related skills and use of digital media in informal and formal education.

Table 1: Overview of the younger cohort

	Gender	Age Range	School Type	Household	Parents' Formal Educational Background	Living Situation
Alina	female	7 – 10	primary	mother, father and older brother (age: 10 – 13)	completed degree/ secondary school certificate	urban
Ben	male	7 – 10	primary	both mothers	both parents: completed degree	urban
Elisa	female	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and older brother (age: 9 – 13)	both parents: completed degree	suburban
Emil	male	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and younger brother (age: 4 – 7)	both parents: completed degree	rural
Eric	male	6 – 10	alternative	mother, father and older brother (age: 9 – 13)	both parents: completed degree	urban
Felix	male	6 – 10	alternative	foster father and two older sisters (age: 8 – 12; 11 – 14)	secondary school certificate	rural
Frieda	female	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and younger sister (age: 2 – 6)	both parents: completed degree	suburban
Henry	male	6 – 10	primary	mother and older sister (age: 11 – 14)	vocational training	urban

Isabell	female	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and younger brother (age: 0 – 4)	completed degree/ secondary school certificate	suburban
Marie	female	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and younger brother (age: 4 – 8)	both parents: completed degree	urban
Oda	female	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and older brother (age: 10 – 13)	both parents: completed degree	urban
Oskar	male	6 – 10	primary	mother, father and older sister (age: 9 – 13)	both parents: completed degree	urban
Paul	male	6 – 10	primary	mother and father	both parents: completed degree	urban
Piet	male	7 – 10	primary	mother, father and younger sister (age: 3 – 7)	secondary school certificate	urban
Sophie	female	6 – 10	alternative	mother and older sister (age: 9 – 13); at t1 and t2: father	completed degree/ secondary school certificate	rural

Empirical Results

The empirical findings provide a deep and long-term insight into the media socialisation of children. A preliminary overview of the sample indicates varying socio-economic and educational backgrounds of the families, as well as different family structures (e.g., blended families and various sibling constellations), and in the cases of Felix and Sophie, children attending alternative school types. Furthermore, an overview of the families' media ensembles made it clear that there are major differences in the equipment children can theoretically access within this social domain. There are not only 'traditional' media such as books, music systems or radios, televisions and gaming consoles, but also various digital devices such as computers, tablets, smartphones or smart home devices to various degrees. In addition to these differences, a closer examination of differences concerning (digital) media usage will be highlighted: first, on the level of developments and differences in the individual media repertoires of the children (1) – including their digital devices and media usage; second, on the level of competencies the children feel in different areas of their own media use and to what extent parents attribute or ascribe them certain skills (2); finally, the role of digital media in educational institutions will be emphasised by highlighting differences in the areas of informal and formal media usage (3).

Differences in media repertoires

First, there are strong differences in the media devices accessible to the children between the cases, but also across the three surveys. One fundamental observation is that some

children's media repertoires are more influenced by print media, while others are more influenced by digital media. For example, at the time of the first survey, some children had access to rather few media (devices), such as Felix, who only used a family tablet and books. Felix's father set guidelines for the use of the tablet, on which Felix was only allowed to play selected games for a limited time. In contrast, Isabell, for example, had a very diverse range of media at her disposal: she had her own CD player and an own smartphone, used the family tablet as well as her father's laptop and computer, her parents' smartphones, the family TV and the DVD player connected to it, an electronic reading pen and books. Her parents also imposed time restrictions on the various technical devices, and she was only allowed to use some devices together with one parent. The two exemplary cases presage the differences in media equipment becoming evident at the beginning of primary school as well as various restrictions imposed by the parents to limit access.

Nevertheless, in all cases, access to various media tends to widen over the survey waves. Over time, the use of gaming consoles is added for some children, or they receive their own devices like tablets and smartphones. This does not always mean that children are allowed to access these devices without parental control. When purchasing new devices, most parents implement new time or content-related rules for the use or impose technical restrictions. Furthermore, parents often grant longer access to the devices available in the family. For example, in the third survey wave, Felix is allowed to use the family's gaming console, and Isabell now has her own smart speaker in her bedroom. Her father tells us about Isabell's usage of the new device:

“So, I really think the big step is Alexa [smart speaker] because you can do a lot through it, like filling in shopping lists and listening to audio dramas, music, and so on. So, that's actually the biggest change.” (Isabell's father, t3)

Differences are also evident in the specific applications the children use. These include various types of audio content (such as playing music or listening to audio dramas on different devices), audiovisual offerings (such as watching linear television programs, series, or movies via streaming services and platforms like YouTube), as well as digital gaming (on smartphones, tablets, or consoles). While these media practices are partly bound to available devices, digital devices offer a great variety of possible applications. For example, there are children like Frieda, who are only allowed to watch series on the family tablet. In contrast, Isabell conducts online research with her father, watches YouTube videos together with him, or is even allowed to play games on the tablet. Similarly to the available media (devices), the media practices of the children vary significantly over time. Children are often allowed to use a wider range of applications as time goes on, and they become increasingly interested in new or different topics. At the same time, other media practices are losing importance: for example, electronic reading

pens, which many children, including Isabell and Emil, feel they have "outgrown". Children have significantly varying access to various media practices.

Differences in media-related skills

At the beginning of primary school, both children and parents express different extents of children's media-related skills. Frieda, for example, said of herself that she is not yet very familiar with technical devices and her mother also emphasised: "She is allowed to use the laptop on her own. But of course, I have to switch it on for her. Because she can't type in what it is yet." (Frieda's mother, t1). Emil's mother described how her son is often still emotionally and temporally overwhelmed when it comes to using media. In addition, he was not yet able to judge for himself when he was using the screen too much. This is a common finding for the majority of the children interviewed. Sometimes children and parents described different perceptions of children's skills, e.g., with Felix and his foster father: Felix felt that he is very competent, especially when it comes to playing digital games, whereas his father thought that his son did not yet know a lot about media (topics) and was often overwhelmed by his own time management. Isabell's father was also aware of deficits in his daughter's media-related skills – in particular the "addictive potential" of digital media offerings, which still captivated Isabell. However, he tried to actively promote his daughter's media skills. As an IT specialist, it is very important to him that Isabell is able to handle media well and he also takes her to informal media education courses on coding, for example: "Um, yes, the technical things, uh, as an IT specialist (...) I try to introduce her to a few things." (Isabell's father, t1). There are similar approaches in a small proportion of our families, in which parents try to strengthen their children's media-related skills through their own involvement.

Across the whole cohort, it becomes evident that the children gain media-related skills with increasing age, according to their own statements and those of their parents. On the one hand, this growth varies depending on the basic level of skills mentioned in the first interview: Children who were generally perceived as less competent also tended to develop less advanced media-related skills over time, with a widening gap in children's competencies being observed. On the other hand, there are different increases in media-related skills depending on children's media interests and support from other actors or social domains. Frieda and her mother report, for example, that she sometimes still needs support in using digital media. However, her mother mentions Frieda quickly acquires missing operating skills. Furthermore, in the third interview Frieda searches for information online independently if she wants to know more about a specific topic. So in Frieda's case both her own interest and the support of her parents are important for increasing media-related skills. Emil also needs support in using his own and school media (applications). His mother states furthermore that he is still too naïve to use certain devices alone:

“There may certainly be classmates at that age who are already doing all that, but for me they're still too childish, maybe not, that's the wrong word, but too naïve, too blue-eyed to really let them go for it.” (Emil's mother, t3)

However, he is particularly curious about other digital media functions, likes to test them out and sometimes looks for help in online forums. His friends are important influencing factors in this matter, as they exchange relevant topics and facts. Felix's perceptions of him and his foster father are still very different in t3. In the third survey, he perceives himself as being very quick to acquire user skills in relation to digital media and gaming in particular. His foster father, on the contrary, describes Felix as often still overwhelmed by his own media use and setting time limits, even at the end of primary school. He would not yet understand, for example, that his father can view the media times on the tablet and the gaming console:

“Because I check that too, yes? So, these are things, when he now [...] that's also something he doesn't understand, [...] that of course everything he does there, that (knocking) you can determine that with al [...]. Yes, what if I somehow [...] I can look on the PlayStation to see which games have been played on it and/ he has played them. Or on the [...] on the iPad I can (knock) look up what/ what was started last or something. He notices that, [...] he hasn't figured that out yet either.” (Felix's father, t3)

Over time, Isabell becomes even more self-confident in her media use, she uses them independently and tends to secretly circumvent her parents' rules regarding digital media without them noticing. Her father continues to emphasise the importance of Isabell acquiring technical skills to him. In our sample, Isabell represents an example of the most pronounced media-related skills. In general, a larger gap in the media-related skills of children can be identified at t3. This gap develops on the basis of children's own interests and media practices but are also influenced by the social circumstances that may more or less support and encourage the acquisition of such competencies.

Differences in formal and informal media usage in educational institutions

All in all, digital media hardly played a role in the school context for the entire cohort in the first two surveys. Instead, teachers focused on print media or other analogue teaching tools (e.g., blackboards, overhead projectors or document cameras). This changed abruptly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Digital media was used as part of the distance schooling strategy in the majority of primary schools attended by the children interviewed. Most schools used chats and video conferences to keep in touch with the children, as was the case with Frieda and Emil. In Isabell's case, only video calls were used together with the whole class and parents had the option of picking up paper assignments at school instead of digital learning options. Felix's school, on the contrary, was one of the few schools in this sample that did not use any digital media to teach the children, even

during distance learning. As part of the alternative school concept, they used only work materials printed out by the school.

The "special phase" of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic led to a significant increase in digital media use for a limited period of time, not in all, but in a large proportion of the primary schools in the sample. It became evident that the children often needed support from their parents with the technical implementation since the media applications used in school did not, or at least only partially, align with the children's private media repertoires. For example, Emil had to be supported by his mother in using the program his school worked with.

After the social restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic, however, there was an abrupt decline in these digital teaching and learning practices. Schools switched back to face-to-face teaching with conventional materials. For example, Emil and Isabell hardly ever use digital media in the course of formal learning after the phase of distance schooling:

Emil: "Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Teams, we always use that."

Interviewer: "At school?"

Emil: "Yes."

Interviewer: "Uh-huh. [...] What does always mean, how [...] how often [...] do you use [...] how often do you use it?"

Emil: "Not really, almost not at all."

Interviewer: "[...] Okay, what does almost not at all mean?"

Emil: "No, we used that during the COVID-19 period." (Emil, t3)

In Frieda's school, media projects are implemented sporadically towards the end of her primary school years, e.g., the children programmed together with LEGO Mindstorm during a project week:

Frieda's mother: "But at school, you don't use stuff like that, right?"

Frieda: "Only once, for the Lego project. And the projector."

Frieda's mother: "Okay, the projector. Yeah. But you don't do anything on the laptop or computer or something like that?"

Frieda: "Only once in religion, we had to do some research."

Frieda's mother: "Ah, okay. Well, I think they should also do some research, but then at home on the internet, yeah." (Frieda and her mother, t3)

These and similar exceptions in the use of digital media are typical for the entire sample. However, many of the children, including Frieda, would like to see digital media used more often in the classroom. The parents have diverging opinions about this matter: Isabell's parents, for example, would like to see more use of digital media in the school context so Isabell can learn basic media skills for her later education and career. Other parents, such as Felix's father, hold the view that children should not (yet) use digital

media at school. Thus, there appears to be a different set of values held by children, parents, and schools regarding the use and acquisition of digital media, which can create another divide.

Even if fewer digital media are used in the classroom in schools, the children themselves nonetheless exchange information about their media practices and interests in school. This hints towards another divide between the importance of (digital) media in formal and informal education. Isabell tends to be an exception here: she does not use or talk about media with classmates. In contrast, since Frieda has her own smartphone discussions about that device increase:

Interviewer: "Then in your class or who all already has or who all already has a smartphone?"

Frieda: "All except two [...]"

Interviewer: "Okay. That means you wanted to be able to have a say, didn't you?"

Frieda: "Yes."

Interviewer: "Did you also want to be able to use WhatsApp or why exactly?"

Frieda: "Because everyone had one and because I wanted to have a say and so on." (Frieda, t3)

Such developments towards increasing discussion in combination with the acquisition of new devices are also evident in some of the other cases of the sample. Even before the acquisition of their first personal smartphones, they are a topic of discussion among Emil and his friends, as well as the use of initial social media applications (especially messengers). However, Emil and his classmates maintain a consistent interest in a specific media topic throughout all survey waves: Minecraft. Such media topics are frequently discussed among Felix and his classmates, too: the children talk about various movies, series, and video games. This happens despite the fact that the parents in the class have made a "media agreement". The parents had collectively agreed to not buy their children own smartphones yet. So, there are also differences among peers and their media practices and topics in the school context.

Summary

In line with the research on the various levels of the digital divide, differences in access to media, interests, practices, skills, and ultimately the consequences for formal education within the ConKids sample could be shown. In addition to the omnipresence of digital media in society, the other trends of deep mediatisation for children's media repertoires are also becoming evident: It can be seen that children's media repertoires continue to differentiate over the course of primary school. Children have access to more familial media devices as well as they get more own devices. Their media practices and interests become increasingly diverse and go hand in hand with differences in their media-related abilities and skills. Thus, in this sample, there are signs of the digital divide on all three

levels: not only in terms of access to different media equipment but also concerning individual media interests. These differences, in a second step, lead to diverse media practices and associated skills, reflecting the second-level digital divide. The impact of the digital divide on formal learning becomes particularly evident during the period of distance schooling due to the COVID-19 pandemic. In the majority of cases, teachers used remote learning functions, which made the use of digital media necessary. Only when children had access to the necessary infrastructure, were familiar with media practices, and possessed the relevant media-related skills, they could participate in online lessons. The gap between private media usage and school requirements, nevertheless, is significant both before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, the children's discussions about own media practices with peers, can hardly be linked to the formal media usage in schools.

It is evident that social influences, especially the parents, take an important part in reproducing the digital divide: on the one hand, they enable different media devices and practices to their children. Simply due to the fact that they make a variety of different media available to their children, set an example through their own media usage or allow them to use these. On the other hand, they place different values and demands on their children's media usage as well as media-related skills and therefore support the respective activities more or less. This support also depends on the media competencies and media educational skills of the parents themselves. In consequence, if they were capable of assisting their children in using technical solutions for school-related media practices continued to play a crucial role in determining whether children could participate in classes, for example, during the time of distance schooling or not. But other social influencing factors also play a role in terms of media equipment, interests, and skills. The fact that the digital divide is already evident in this sample, which tends to have a higher socio-economic and educational background for German society, shows a strong influence of social conditions on the appropriation of digital media by children.

Challenges for educational institutions

To address these varying conditions regarding children's private media usage, different challenges for educational institutions derive which they will have to face in the future to encounter the detected aspects of the digital divide:

1. Significant differences in the private media repertoire and children's media-related skills are evident from the beginning of primary school and are exacerbated as they advance in age. In order to address these disparities and support children in developing media-related competencies as they grow older, formal educational institutions must take into account these individual prerequisites. This requires, on the one hand, more research in the area of media socialisation to provide decision-makers and teachers with information about possible starting

points. On the other hand, curricula should provide the opportunity to allocate time and resources to address these differences.

2. The gap between children's private media repertoires as well as associated skills and the fit to the school's media ensemble creates additional obstacles for them. If they struggle to cope with digital requirements due to the low fit between the two worlds, they lack the resources to understand and implement educational content. In particular, distance schooling during the COVID-19 pandemic has shown that parents may need to support their children. Depending on parents' capabilities, however, they may not always be able to adequately assist their children in completing digital tasks for formal learning. Additionally, there should be a focus on developing media-related and media education skills of (prospective) teachers. Only if they know how to build on the children's media repertoire in their lessons, they can create a bridge between the two "worlds". If beyond the educational institutions' digital offerings were more closely aligned with private experiences, children with fewer social and media-related resources would not be left behind.

3. Future challenges by deep mediatisation and further digitisation have to be considered. These showed already in the exceptional situation of the COVID-19 pandemic where the digital divide became especially evident as children, parents and teachers were overstrained. However, the media environment does not stop at this point; keeping an eye on its changes and new developments (as currently illustrated by discussions around the topic of AI, for example) will continue to be of great importance in the future. To be better prepared for such exceptional situations and future developments, there is a need for better implementation of appropriate digital media applications in the curriculum as well as in the training and further education of teachers.

In general, it is important to keep in mind that the promotion of digital skills and media literacy begins as early as possible in educational institutions and is designed inclusively for all children with their different prerequisites. This is the only way to counteract the digital divide and offer all children the same opportunities for digital participation in adulthood.

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